

A STACKED A-TO-D CONVERTER FOR INCREASED RADAR SIGNAL PROCESSOR DYNAMIC RANGE

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Abstract — The need for increased dynamic range at the input to the radar digital signal processor has increased steadily over the last decade or so. This has been the result of lower expected radar cross sections, the need for better clutter suppression, and the desire to operate without Sensitivity Time Control (STC) in some radar applications. The Analog-to-Digital Converter (ADC) is the most significant bottleneck in achieving this needed dynamic range (DR). In this paper, an approach for improving the effective DR utilizing multiple ADCs is described. The ADCs are arranged in parallel channels with different gains and the approach is referred to as a "Stacked A-to-D Converter", or "Stacked ADC". Detailed results are presented for an experimental brassboard system assembled to demonstrate and evaluate the concept.

I. INTRODUCTION

In new radar systems, the desired dynamic range often exceeds the performance of available analog-to-digital converters (ADCs). In order to overcome this limitation, radar designers seek to accommodate the total required dynamic range (DR) through the addition of Sensitivity Time Control (STC), Automatic Gain Control (AGC), and use of Intermediate Frequency (IF) limiting amplifiers. Such IF limiters usually have their limit level adjusted to correspond to the maximum dynamic range of the A-to-D converter (ADC).

Expected lower values of the radar cross section of aircraft and missiles has increased sensitivity and clutter-suppression requirements by several orders of magnitude, and corresponding improvements in dynamic range and radar stability are needed. While significant advances in ADC technology have taken place, progress has been slower than that seen for computer memory and arithmetic units. As a result, available ADCs do not meet many new advanced radar requirements.

In this paper, an approach is described which effectively overcomes these limitations and provides accurate A-to-D conversion with a true instantaneous dynamic range not previously available. The technique uses multiple, parallel ADCs, each connected to the radar IF through an amplifier with a different gain value. After channel equalization, and

selection of the output channel with the largest linear signal, a total dynamic range is realized, which is much greater than possible with a single ADC. Individual ADC limitations on signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) and spurious-free dynamic range (SFDR) will, however, not be improved by this approach so that the main restriction of this new approach is an output signal-to-noise-and-distortion (SINAD) which can be no greater than that available from each individual ADC.

In order to demonstrate the feasibility and performance limitations of this concept, an experimental "Stacked ADC" was implemented and detailed test results are presented.

II. RADAR DYNAMIC RANGE REQUIREMENTS

A list of potential radar needs for increased dynamic range at the input to the digital signal processor (DSP) is found in Table I. Maintaining the best possible radar sensitivity at all

TABLE I

RADAR NEEDS FOR INCREASED DYNAMIC RANGE

- Maintain optimum sensitivity in all range-angle resolution cells
 - Avoid global desensitization
- Maximize clutter attenuation
 - Keep clutter peaks near ADC top range
 - Avoid clutter saturation or limiting
- Measure cross section accurately for target identification and STC
- Use zero-Doppler clutter map for residue suppression in MTI or pulse-Doppler filters
 - Needed in Moving Target Detection (MTD) radars
- Process high level EMI without desensitization or loss of data

radar detection ranges of interest is of particular importance in the case of the detection of low-cross-section targets where a significant detection margin may not be available, even at relatively short range. Often the use of STC and AGC will adversely affect the detection performance against such targets.

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Clutter attenuation (or cancellation) is often an important radar requirement. For best performance, this requires linear processing over the full clutter dynamic range since any non-linearity will result in the generation of inter-modulation products, and therefore lowered clutter attenuation [1].

The accurate measurement of target (as well as clutter) amplitude over their full dynamic range is frequently required for target recognition and discrimination, as well as for the suppression of false alarms caused by clutter residues. Again, non-linearity will result in erroneous measurements.

In a high-power long-range radar system, the dynamic range of signals, noise, and clutter at the input can be as high as 80-100 dB above thermal noise, even prior to pulse compression. Such values exceed the capability of currently available ADCs by 20-40 dB. It is this shortfall, which is the focus of the Stacked ADC technique for dynamic range extension, as discussed in the following sections.

III. EXTENDING THE ADC DYNAMIC RANGE

Techniques, which have been used, or proposed, for increasing the effective dynamic range of a radar signal processor beyond the inherent ADC capability, are listed in Table II. The conventional uses of STC and AGC were mentioned previously and have been used extensively in radar systems.

TABLE II CANDIDATE TECHNIQUES FOR INCREASING DSP DYNAMIC RANGE	
•	Sensitivity Time Control (STC)
•	Adaptive attenuation (switched gain)
•	Range-cell to range-cell analog gain control
•	Digital feedback to analog attenuator
•	DR compression at ADC input, expansion at output (companding)
•	Use N ADCs in parallel ($\Delta = 10 \log_{10}(N)$ dB improvement for uncorrelated noise)
•	Use N Stacked ADCs spaced Δ dB channel-to-channel (improvement $\Delta(N-1)$ dB)
•	Wait for improved ADCs (Σ - Δ , Cryogenics)
•	Analog Devices AD6644 @ FS=65 MHz provides ~73 dB SINAD and about 60 dB DR (0.2 dB NF loss)

The technique of digital feedback to an analog attenuator uses a control signal, originating in the signal processor, to control an analog attenuator in the receiver in order to continuously ensure that signal, noise, and clutter levels fall inside the dynamic range of the ADC [2]. However, with this type of approach, it is difficult to maintain low switching transients and sufficient accuracy to support a high value of clutter suppression.

When the output noise of individual ADCs is independent channel-to-channel, an improvement in SNR, and

consequently DR, can be achieved by connecting N ADCs in parallel and sum their outputs. However, since the theoretical improvement (in dB) is $10 \cdot \log_{10}(N)$ a large number of ADCs would be required to realize a substantial SNR improvement. Also, since spurious responses are likely to be correlated channel-to-channel, this would ultimately limit the performance improvement.

The Stacked ADC concept, as described in the next section, is similar to the above mentioned paralleled ADC approach, except that ADCs are connected to the IF through amplifiers with different gains, and their outputs are combined by scaling and selection rather than by summing.

IV. A "STACKED ADC" PRINCIPLE

The basic concept of the proposed Stacked ADC approach is illustrated by Fig. 1. This diagram assumes that direct IF-to-digital conversion is used at the final IF frequency of the

Fig. 1. Block diagram of Stacked ADC concept.

radar. The real IF samples at the ADC output must then be converted to complex I&Q samples by finite impulse response (FIR) filters in a process often referred to as digital down conversion (DDC) [3,4]. As is well known, in order for the direct IF conversion approach to prevent aliasing of positive and negative frequency spectral components, the ADC sampling rate must be related to the radar IF frequency according to:

$$f_s = \frac{4 \cdot f_{IF}}{2 \cdot M - 1} \quad (1)$$

where M can take any value M=1, 2, 3, etc. Thus, candidate sampling rates are $4.0 f_{IF}$, $1.33 f_{IF}$, $0.80 f_{IF}$, $0.57 f_{IF}$, etc. The maximum non-aliased bandwidth, which can be supported, is then $B_{max} = f_s / 2$ and band-pass filters must be included prior to the ADC sampling to restrict the bandwidth of signals, clutter and noise to this value, within specified error limits. If the required Nyquist bandwidth is less than $f_s/2$, some relaxation of the above sampling rate requirement can

be tolerated at the expense of a more complex DDC filter design.

Prior to the ADC, the IF path is split into N parallel channels and incrementally amplified in steps of Δ dB. In the hardware implementation described here $\Delta = 6$ dB was used. In general the gain increment used, will be a trade-off between the overlap in the DR between pairs of channels and the number of channels needed to realize a certain required dynamic range.

Before the N channels can be multiplexed into a single data stream, equalization in each channel is required to correct the raw ADC numbers for the different values of IF-gain used and to correct for any channel-to-channel gain and phase errors caused by hardware imperfections. The equalizer can take the form of an FIR filter with adaptively computed coefficients, or simply as a complex gain factor with a value determined by channel-to-channel comparisons. The latter approach was used in the experimental system described later, but a FIR equalizer may result in improved performance. The values of the complex weights used to equalize the channels are determined by pair-wise comparisons of adjacent channels with the most sensitive channel used as the reference. This comparison may be based on dedicated pilot signals injected into the radar receiver, or by using actual target, clutter, and jamming returns received during radar operation. The latter strategy was employed in the experimental system described here.

Finally, the N channels are combined into a single data stream, but with a total dynamic range, which is increased by $(N - 1) \cdot \Delta$ dB over that of a single channel. The combination of channels is based on a strategy, which, on a range-sample-to-range-sample basis, selects the output from the ADC with the highest non-limiting output. This selection must take into account the spreading of limited ADC samples due to the length of the DDC FIR filter(s).

A somewhat more conservative combination strategy can be implemented when all data from a complete Coherent Processing Interval (CPI) is stored in memory. For each range sample, the output data would then be taken from the same ADC across the entire CPI. This selection is again based on no-ADC saturation for any of the received returns across the entire CPI. This modified approach would ensure that clutter suppression will not be degraded by errors in the channel-to-channel equalization but will not be further discussed in this paper.

V. AN EXPERIMENTAL STACKED ADC SYSTEM

A brassboard, experimental Stacked ADC system was constructed using connectorized evaluation boards, filters, amplifiers, and power dividers. This approach was selected to obtain realistic performance results with a minimum of development.

A block diagram of the experimental Stacked ADC system is shown in Fig. 2. With the ADC sampling rate selected at 40 MS/s, the intermediate frequency input was defined to be $f_{IF} = 10$ MHz using $M = 1$ in Eq. (1). A total of four channels was implemented using a channel $\Delta = 6$ dB for a total DR improvement of 18 dB. For the same number of

Fig. 2. Brassboard Stacked A/D converter system.

paralleled ADCs the SNR improvement of the output sum would be only 6 dB. A practical issue in the integration of an ADC into any radar system is the need to maintain extreme linearity over the normal input voltage range to the ADC, while limiting the input amplitudes to a value less than the maximum allowed voltage. In the experimental system, the ADC was protected against excess input voltage by a Harris (now Intersil) HFA 1130 linear/limiting amplifier. This device permits the setting of gain and limit level using external components. Freedom from harmonics and inter-modulation products at the output of these amplifiers is of critical importance for output voltages within the ADCs linear dynamic range. For a required operating range at the ADC input of ± 1 V and an absolute maximum input of

TABLE III	
LINEAR/LIMITING AMPLIFIER SPECIFICATION	
• Model	HFA1130
• Rise and fall time	<3.2 ns
• 2 nd harmonic distortion at 2 V peak-to-peak output:	-56 dB typ, -48 dB min
• 3 rd harmonic intermod at 2 V peak-to-peak output:	-80 dB typ, -65 dB min
• Settling time to 0.1%	11 ns typical

± 2 V, the HFA 1130 provides performance as summarized in Table III. As seen in this table, the 2nd harmonic and 3rd order inter-modulation products at the linear dynamic range limits have typical values of -56 dB and -80 dB, respectively.

The ADCs were 14-bit, 65 MHz Analog Devices AD6644, mounted on an Analog Devices evaluation board. The ADC clock was obtained from an external 40 MHz crystal oscillator locked to a 10 MHz reference from a signal generator. The specification for this ADC is given in Table IV and shows a typical SINAD of 74 dB for a 19.5 MHz input and a 65 MS/s sampling rate. An input amplifier with a

TABLE IV ANALOG-TO-DIGITAL CONVERTER SPECIFICATION	
•	Analog Devices evaluation board
•	A/D converter Analog Devices AD6644
•	Number of bits 14
•	Sampling rate 65 MS/s
•	SINAD for input at 19.5 MHz is 71 dB min, 74 dB typ
•	Linear range input voltage 2.0 V peak-to-peak
•	Absolute maximum input voltage is 5.0 V peak-to-peak

gain of $G=17$ dB was used to overcome the loss of the $I:6$ power divider. The input amplifier has a third order output intercept point at 38 dBm, which is necessary for a low-distortion amplification of the IF signal.

The test configuration for the experimental Stacked ADC system utilized two signal generators with their outputs summed to provide single or two-tone inputs, and the ADC outputs were recorded simultaneously using a Logic Analyzer (HP16717A).

The harmonics from the signal generators (-57 to -59 dBc), as well as those generated by the first amplifier, were suppressed by a low-pass filter inserted prior to the $I:6$ power divider. This setup allows two-tone inter-modulation tests to be made, providing an effective means of quantitative performance verification of the final Stacked ADC system.

Outputs from the four Amplifier/Limiters, for a two-tone input separated by 25 kHz and set to a maximum level 1 dB below full scale, are shown in Fig. 3. Except for the least sensitive (1X) channel the amplifiers are driven into saturation and limit the output voltage to be within the ADC specification.

A number of tests were made using single-tone and two-tone inputs at different frequencies around the 10 MHz IF-frequency. For each test, a total of 16,384 raw data samples were collected in each channel at the ADC output, using the HP Logic Analyzer.

All subsequent data processing was performed on a PC, using these recorded data samples. MATLAB was used to perform this analysis, which consisted of the processing steps listed in Table V. The first step in the processing implements the digital down conversion (DDC), which recovers the complex I & Q pairs from the ADC IF-samples. This was

Fig. 3. Input to A/D converter in all four channels for two-tone input set at 1 dB below full scale.

done using the standard approach of filtering the odd-even ADC samples, alternating the sign in each sequence and filtering with an 18-tap FIR filter designed to reject negative frequency components by more than 60 dB.

The output magnitude of the DDC in the four channels is shown in Fig. 4 as a function of time for the two-tone input in Fig. 3. The sampling rate is now 20 MHz so that 1000 samples correspond to a time interval of 50 μ s. For each channel, a scale factor was applied to the ADC outputs as shown (1X, 2X, 4X, 8X) to approximately compensate for the different gain values (0 dB, 6 dB, 12 dB, 18 dB) applied to the IF inputs. Only the least sensitive (1X) channel correctly reproduces the complete signal input. In the

Fig. 4. Scaled magnitudes in all channels after DDC.

remaining channels, the combination of ADC limiting and the DDC operation produces an erroneous output during the intervals where limiting occurs. Such data would not be useful for any further radar signal processing.

TABLE V MATLAB PC DATA ANALYSIS	
•	Implement digital down converter (DDC) using FIR filters of length N=18
•	Set saturation flag for each ADC and each range cell <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Any ADC samples >2047 or <-2047 • Broaden by DDC FIR filter length
•	Perform channel-to-channel equalization
•	Selected highest, non-saturated ADC output on a range-cell to range-cell basis
•	Perform spectral analysis using 90 dB Chebyshev window

The fundamental principle of operation the Stacked ADC converter is finally illustrated by the magnitude vs. time plot in Fig. 5, where the output data in each successive range samples (each of 50 ns duration) is taken from the most sensitive channel not affected by ADC limiting. For the two-tone input used here, the most sensitive ADC (8X) contributes to the output over very short periods of time only.

In order to determine what data can be safely obtained from each channel, saturation of the ADC must be monitored sample-to-sample. For the experimental system, as shown in Fig. 2, this was simply done by testing for full-scale positive or negative values at the ADC output. Additionally, the broadening effect of each saturated ADC sample, due to the length of the DDC FIR filters, must be taken into account. For the FIR filter of length 18, each saturated sample will therefore affect an additional 17 samples (each 50 ns duration) at the DDC output. Any sample so tagged was inhibited from the final output shown in Fig. 5.

Finally, a strategy needs to be developed for dynamically obtaining equalization factors for the individual channels. In the experimental system, a simple strategy was implemented in the data analysis to derive the equalization constants for all adjacent pairs of A-to-D channels. The equalization constant

Fig. 5. Magnitude of combined output from non-saturating ADC.

is computed as the average of the complex ratio of all samples for which the most sensitive of the pair of ADCs has a magnitude between full scale and one-half of full scale. Denoting this set of indices in channel L by Ω_L the corresponding equalization factor is:

$$\alpha_{L-1} = \frac{1}{K_L} \sum_{i \in \Omega_L} \frac{y_{i,L}}{y_{i,L-1}} \quad (2)$$

where K_L is the number of samples in the set Ω_L and $y_{i,L}$ and $y_{i,L-1}$ are the complex values in the two channels at index i.

A result of this simple strategy is that the individual equalization constants were based on a different number (K_L) of ratios averaged. In any practical implementation of the Stacked ADC the equalization factors would, however, be obtained from a very large number of samples. Results

Fig. 6. Single-tone spectrum at the output of the 1X ADC.

obtained using the final analysis step are described in the following section.

VI. PERFORMANCE RESULTS FOR THE EXPERIMENTAL STACKED ADC

An initial test of the Stacked ADC system was performed with a single tone input at 12 MHz set at 1 dB below full scale (FS) of the least sensitive ADC channel. The spectrum shown in Fig. 6 was obtained from the 1X ADC channel only (since the other three were in saturation) using a weighting function based on a 90 dB Dolph-Chebyshev function. Since the spectrum represents the complex envelope it is centered at 0 MHz and the single-tone input appears at +2 MHz. The spectrum shows the harmonic response limitations of the system. In Fig. 6 2nd and 3rd harmonics (at 6 MHz and -6 MHz respectively) limit the SINAD to 57.4 dB. With the 20 largest discrete lines in the spectrum removed, a SNR=66.4 dB was calculated. The harmonics are partly due

to the limitations of the HFA1130 (see Table III) but during testing it was further discovered that the HFA1130 in the 8X channel, which was driven strongly into saturation, was reflecting a significant second harmonic, which coupled back into the other three channels through the 1:6 power divider. Similar performance limitations in operational radars due to non-linearities in the amplifiers at the ADC input have been encountered in the past.

Two-tone tests of the Stacked ADC were next carried out as described previously. Again the peak level into the 1X

Fig. 7. Spectrum at output of Stacked ADC converter with two-tone input and including equalization.

ADC channel was set to 1 dB below FS but in this case the spectrum of the final Stacked ADC output was obtained as shown in Fig. 7 using equalization constants derived according to Eq. (2). For the two-tone case a SINAD=55.0 dB was calculated and with the 20 largest discretes removed a SNR=61.0 dB was obtained. A total of 8192 complex samples were available in the combined output for this spectral analysis. The combined result for a number of input frequencies is summarized in Fig. 8. The top curve was obtained by re-equalizing the four channels at each input frequency, while the lower curve used a channel equalization derived at 9.5 MHz. The degradation due to harmonics reflected from the Amplifier/Limiter can most likely be removed by adding buffer amplifiers at the output of the 1:6 divider. The harmonics at the Amplifier/Limiter output would be difficult to suppress with low-pass filters due to the large relative bandwidth of the 10 MHz IF. However, if the IF frequency is changed to 30 MHz (corresponding to $M=2$ in Eq. (1)) filtering of the harmonics would become much easier. Such modifications will be tested on a future version of the Stacked ADC.

Fig. 8. SINAD performance of Stacked ADC system across the band with two-tone input

VII. CONCLUSIONS

Experimental results for a Stacked ADC system, as described in this report, have demonstrated the feasibility of increasing the effective dynamic range in a practical radar signal processor from 60-65 dB to 78-83 dB while maintaining a SINAD of 50-55 dB against a two-tone input signals over a wide bandwidth. Major sources of this SINAD degradation, relative to that specified for individual ADCs, are the harmonics generated in the Amplifier/Limiting amplifiers. Approaches for eliminating this degradation have been defined and will be implemented in future tests of the Stacked ADC concept. However, it should also be kept in mind that current radar systems are likely to suffer from similar degradation due to harmonics and inter-modulation products at the radar receiver/ADC interface.

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